

**THE ORDER OF DRIP IRRIGATION OF CORN VARIETIES AS THE
MAIN CROP**

Jurayev F.U. Professor Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management

*Isayeva L.B. doctoral student of the Department "Water Management and
melioration"*

Najmiddinov M. M. student of the direction "Water Management and melioration"

Bobirova M.B. student of the direction "Water Management and melioration"

*Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Engineers National Research
University Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management*

Annotation: Corn is considered the most valuable, high – yield grain crop food, fodder, technical and agrotechnical importance. As food, cornstarch's Dogi is used. His Dogi is considered very nutritious and has an average content of 10,6% cutlet, 1,4% ash substances. But, in corn grain, the protein content is low. For this reason, bread is closed by adding 25-30% bug'doy flour to the corn flour. Since corn Dogi has a lot of precipitation (4,3-5,0%) in its composition, it quickly hurts it. Grain porridge is separated in special machines, flour is prepared from the rest, because in the composition of corn porridge contains about 25 – 40% fat, from which the oil used for food is prepared. In addition, cereals from corn cereals are prepared, during the milk – wax ripening period, it can be used as food, in which it is fried (tonsils) and boiled. During this period, it is also possible to prepare a konserva from its grain. As fodder, cornstarch's dog and STEM are used. His dog is considered very nutritious (1 kg of corn dog has 1,34 kg of nutrient unit), it is given to domestic poultry and goods in whole or in Groats.

Keywords: Corn, high yield, fodder, nutritious, corn Dani, corn flour.

Currently, attention is being paid to improving the land reclamation situation in the agricultural and water sector, increasing the efficiency of canals and collector-

trenches in the supply of water to the irrigated areas of farmer farms. Shular in addition, the effective use of Land-Water Resources requires the improvement of modern resurstejamkor irrigation techniques and technologies. In the strategy of action on further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan "... in order to increase the competitiveness of the national economy, it is necessary to reduce the consumption of energy and resources, to introduce a wide range of resource-intensive technologies into production." In this regard, it is important to carry out research work on increasing the fertility of lands on the basis of the development and application of resurstejamkor irrigation methods of crops and the water use plan. The world is engaged in purposeful research on the use of land and water resources and improvement of the melioration condition of the soil. In this regard, the implementation of large-scale anti-erosion research in irrigated areas, the creation of techniques and technologies for the protection of land and Water Resources, the introduction of soil-protecting crops into the structure of arable areas is one of the important tasks in the field of implementation with oats. The development of livestock is one of the most important issues in the provision of environmentally friendly food products to the population, increasing the stock of fodder for livestock. Corn is a valuable, fertile, cereal crop in multi-band use. From cornstarch it is possible to get a good concentrate, Blue Mass and silage. 1 kg of grain contains 1,34 units of nutrients. Silage, prepared when cornstarchs enter the milk-wax ripening period, is the best food for livestock.

At 100 kg of silage there are 24 feed units. In the preparation of land for planting corn, phosphorus (ammonium per 150-200 kg/ha or suprifos per 300-350 kg/ha) fertilizer is given using the technique of spraying NRU-0,5 rubles of fertilizer before planting. If there is a sufficient amount of rotten manure in the farmer's farm, it is ground with the help of fertilizing techniques. Driving on the ground is carried out at a depth of 25-28 CM. In cases where the surface of the field is uneven, it is leveled with special techniques. Work on eliminating unevenness in a small area can be carried out by hanging rollers on the tractor. After that, the field is made of molasses. Sowing corn on the grain in the spring (for corn, which will be 120 days,

at this time, when sown, farmer farms achieve a high result from grain yield to 3-4 t/ha. The time of germination should not remain until may, otherwise the yield will decrease. The planting period is 10-15 April for the regions located in the Central Region (Tashkent, Sirdarya, Jizzakh, Samarkand and Fergana Valley regions), 2 weeks before that (25-30 march) in the southern regions, and 2 weeks after that (25-30 April) in the northern regions. In the spring term, agrotechnical activities in the planting and maintenance of corn for silage, even seedsarfi, are conducted as they are planted in the grain. Depending on the ripening period, the number of seedlings will vary (for goats – 50-55 thousand Bush/ha; for the middle-late-70 thousand Bush/ha; for the middle-fairy tale and Fairy Tales-80 thousand Bush / ha).

For maize silage, it is considered effective to plant in the spring from intermediate crops or from grain crops with a spike in the summer (fast-growing hybrids of maize at this time, and the highest grain mass is obtained. If the fast-growing hybrids of corn are sown in the spring term, then the yield will sharply decrease to 2-3 t) then it is possible to plant. It is recommended to plant corn only for silage in the northern regions of our republic on the fields that are free of Spike crops. In the spring planting of silos and grain is recommended late-maturing, late-mid-maturing varieties and hybrids of corn ("Uzbekistan-601 ESV", "Uzbekistan-420 VL"), early-mid-maturing, early-maturing varieties and hybrids for cereals in summer ("Karasuv-350 AMV", "Uzbekistan-300 MV"). When using pneumatic SPCH-6 seyalka, the planting depth is 5-6 cm. it consists of 22-25 kg seeds per hectare. Bunda the size of each row is 60 cm, 70 cm and 90 cm. Lee will. 60 cm. li is placed in the matriarchs between 21 cm, 24 cm and 30 cm, and in the matriarchs between 24 cm and 30 cm. 70 cm. li is placed in the matriarchs between 18 cm and 20 cm, and the matriarchs between 26 cm. 90 cm. li is placed in the matriarchs between 14 cm, 16 cm and 20 cm, and in the matriarchs between 16 cm and 20 cm. Seed germination is given if there is a lack of moisture in the ground, so that the seeds germinate after planting. In the spring, after the seeds are planted in the ground, there is a lot of precipitation, the areas on which the resin is formed are surface cultivated with the help of cultivators, or the resin is softened with special

adaptations. If, after sowing the seeds, the humidity on the ground is high and the air temperature drops, the seeds will rot. In this case, re-planting is carried out.

When there are 3-4 leaves after planting, the first cultivar is done, manual chopsticks are done, if there is a large number of seedlings, the yagana work is carried out. When there are a lot of weeds, they are treated with special herbicides. When 5-6 leaves are harvested in corn, the first irrigation is carried out by laying 150-180 kg of urea or 250-300 kg of ammonium nitrate per hectare together with ration. When there are 8-10 leaves on the stem, the second cultivar is made. If the field is pressed by a weed, chupik works are carried out, when 10-12 leaves are formed, watered for the second time along with the second feeding. The fasting of corn is watered for the third time to keep the moisture in the norm during the period when it comes to flowering. This watering will last longer than other irrigation. If during this period there is no emphasis on the norm of irrigation, productivity (40-50%) will decrease sharply. This period interval is 7-10 days. At this time, pollination is carried out on the corn crop. It has been proven based on scientific experiments that give well-pollinated plants a high level yield. In corn, the fourth watering is carried out when there is a period of ripening of milk-wax in the grain, at this time the grains are filled and contain the necessary nutrients. At this time, the highest mass and nutrient is achieved if it is rolled into silage. During the ripening of milk-wax in the silo mowing use Maral, KPI-2,4, e-280-duty combines. It is checked before planting corn on the grain, if the plant is in a period of mummification, it is allowed to harvest tavarbop cereals. Seeds grown on large fields (elite, o'1 hybrids) are carried out when full ripening begins. In this case, Khersones-7, Khersones-9 are used. The work that is carried out before planting corn in the summer consists in the following: fertilizing the ground with phosphorus fertilizer (150-200 kg/ha ammofos or 300-350 kg/ha suprifos), plowing the land (at a depth of 25-28 CM), leveling, scratching and molting. In summer planting, it is recommended to have all the activities that are applied in the spring, and seedling the same. From the hybrids of the corn farmer in the morning ("Karasuv-350 AMV" and "Uzbekistan-300 MV"), it is recommended to plant until 20-25 June and to

obtain silos until 15 July in order to obtain fully ripe grain. Cultivation of corn in angiosperms in the summer agrotechnical measures are carried out like spring planting. It should be taken into account that corn, which is planted in the summer, is rapidly growing. Due to this, it is recommended that the plant quickly undergoes processing, feeding and watering between rows.

In summary, it can be said that the development of water-intensive irrigation technology of prospective maize varieties in the conditions of alluvial soils of the meadow of Bukhara region is an urgent issue, taking into account the importance of growing maize and its use in various sectors of the public economy, in the field of pharmaceuticals, cattle breeding and others, scientific research "Uzbekistan-2001", Borja"of maize, which is planted as the main crop in the soil conditions, Scientific-research work on the cultivation of the"Pioneer" variety is carried out, preliminary results are achieved, and scientific research work in this direction is continuing.

Used literature

- [1]. Jurayev, A. Q., Jurayev, U. A., Atamurodov, B. N., & Najmiddinov, M. M. (2021). Scientific Benefits and Efficiency of Drip Irrigation. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(6), 62-64.
- [2]. Muradov Otabek Ulukbekovich, Kattayev Bobir Sobirovich, Saylichanova Maftuna Komiljonovna, & son of the Islamic Charter of Prayer. (2020). Smart irrigation of agricultural crops. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 3, 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.47494/mesb.2020.3.16>
- [3]. Jurayev, A. Q., Jurayev, U. A., Atamurodov, B. N., & Najmiddinov, M. M. (2021). Aphorisms of Farming in the Method of Kidroponics. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 1(6), 133-135.
- [4]. Atamurodov, S. U. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF IMPROVEMENT OF EMOTIONS BASED ON NATIONAL AND UNIVERSAL VALUES TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS ACTIVITIES. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2022(2), 10-23.

- [5]. Muradov Otabek Ulukbekovich, Saylichanova Maftuna Komiljonovna, Kattayev Bobir Sobirovich, Muzaffarov Mukhridin Murodovich. Determination of efficiency of groundwater use in irrigation of millet planting, Euro-Asia Conferences, 2021/3/31, 131-134.
- [6]. Jurayev, A. Q., Jurayev, U. A., Atamurodov, B. N., & Najmiddinov, M. M. (2021). Cultivation of Corn as a Repeated Crop. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 10, 49-51.
- [7]. Atamurodov, B. N., Ibodov, I. N., Najmiddinov, M. M., & Najimov, D. Q. The Effectiveness of Farming in the Method of Hydroponics. *International Journal of Human Computing Studies*, 3(4), 33-36.
- [8]. Juraev, F. U., Ibodov, I. N., Juraev, A. J., Najimov, D. K., & Isoyeva, L. B. (2021, October). Development of procedures for corn varieties irrigation as main crops. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 868, No. 1, p. 012089). IOP Publishing.
- [9] Исаева, Л. Б., Ибрагимова, А. У. К., Фозилов, Ш. Г. У., & Насуллаев, З. И. У. (2021). ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ РЕСУРСНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ОРОШЕНИЯ ПРИ ПОЛИВЕ КУКУРУЗЫ. *Наука, техника и образование*, (3 (78)), 25-27.
- [10]. Saylixanova M., Davronov A., Isaeva L. PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGY //МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ. – 2020. – С. 405-407.
- [11]. JURAYEV U., KHAMIDOV M. Influence of phytoremediation plants on soil salts //Kiev, Ukraine. – 2012.
- [12] Khamidav, M.K., Balla, D., Hamidov, A.M., Juraev, U.A. Using collector-drainage water in saline and arid irrigation areas for adaptation to climate Chang. 2020. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 422 (1), 012121
- [13]. Xamidov M.X., Joraev U.A. Sniceniya mineralizatsii gallektorna-drenajnix VAD // Agrarnaya Nauga. 2016. № 6. С. 2-3.

- [14] Khamidov M.X., Zhuraev U.A. Influence of phytoremediation plants on soil salts // innovative technologies in water management complex. – Ukraine, Rovno, 2012. - What? 32-34.
- [15] Balla Dagma, Ahmad Namidav, Khamidav Muhammadghan, O.About us Improvement of drainage water quality through biological methods: a case study in the Bukhara region of Uzbekistan // European Science overview. - Austria Vienna. – 2016. Page not found (05.00.00. №3).
- [16]. Fazliev, J., Khaitova, I., Atamurodov, B., Rustamova, K., Ravshanov, U., & Sharipova, M. (2019). EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING THE WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IRRIGATED FARMING. *Интернаука*, (21-3), 35-37.
- [17]. Muradov Otabek Ulukbekovich, Saylichanova Maftuna Komiljonovna, Kattayev Bobir Sobirovich, Muzaffarov Mukhriddin Murodovich. Determination of efficiency of groundwater use in irrigation of millet planting, Euro-Asia Conferences, 2021/3/31, 131-134.
- [18]. Muradov A.U., Kattaev B.S., Saylichanova M. K. // The use of sprinkler irrigation in the cultivation of agricultural crops // " Proceeding of the ICECRS.Conference of Management of Islamic Education Leadership in the Era of Revol 4.0 4.0 "conference. - Indonesia 2020.
- [19]. AQ Jurayev, UA Jurayev, BN Atamurodov, MM Najmiddinov, Scientific Benefits and Efficiency of Drip Irrigation, Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication 2021/12/2 62-64 st.
- [20]. UA Jurayev, AQ Jurayev, BN Atamurodov, Application of provided irrigation technologies in irrigated agriculture, International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 2021/12/1 164-166
- [21]. AQ Jurayev, UA Jurayev, BN Atamurodov, MM Najmiddinov, Cultivation of Corn as a Repeated Crop, European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630) 2021/11/29 49-51 st.

[22]. UA Jurayev, A. Jurayev, B. Atamurodov Application of Provided Irrigation Technologies in Irrated Agriculture, - International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 2021 164-166 st.

[23]. Жураев А. К., Саксонов У. С. BUXORO VOHASIDA KUZGI BUG ‘DOYNI SUG ‘ORISH MUDDATLARI VA ME ‘YORLARINI ILMIY ASOSLASH //ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ. – 2019. – №. 6.

[24]. Жураев А. К., Саксонов У. С. BUG ‘DOY O ‘SIMLIGINING BIOLOGIYASI HAMDA AGROTEKNIKASI //ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ. – 2019. – №. 6.